

INVESTIGATIONS ON THE THERMAL LOAD AND ACTIVE THERMAL LOAD REDUCTION DURING LASER PROCESSING OF CFRP

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the thermal load and the active thermal load reduction during laser drilling of CFRP using a nanosecond-pulsed high-power disk laser. The investigations employed different cooling configurations, applying active gas flow cooling to the test specimens. These arrangements involved cooling on the top surface only, cooling on both sides, the top surface and the bottom surface and no cooling applied as reference state. The top surface and bottom surface temperatures were measured by thermography during the laser processing of a multiple borehole pattern, supporting the evaluation of the cooling effectiveness. The heat affected zone (HAZ) of laser drilled cross-section specimens was measured, serving as an indicator for the thermal load brought into the material. The temperature and HAZ results were compared to laser processing without the use of active cooling for heat dissipation.

The results revealed a distinct reduction in surface temperatures when gas flow cooling was applied to the top surface in comparison to processing without gas flow cooling. The surface temperatures were further reduced when gas flow cooling was applied to both the top and bottom surfaces of the test specimen. The evaluation of the HAZ revealed a good correlation between the cooling option, the temperatures measured and the resulting HAZ.

The cooling method applying gas flow to both the top and bottom surfaces of the test specimen proved to be both simple and effective, significantly reducing the thermal load during laser processing of CFRP. This serves to minimize the delay times typically required for laser processing, thus leading to higher efficiency at a constantly low thermal load.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to expanding industrial applications with a requirement on lightweight design and energy efficiency, such as the aerospace, automotive, transportation and energy sectors, the demand of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) is continuously increasing. CFRP materials provide outstanding properties but yet major resistances to the dissemination are high manufacturing and processing costs. Well-developed machining techniques such as milling, drilling or waterjet cutting can be used for the processing of a wide variety of materials but when it comes to composite materials they often suffer from high tool wear, insufficient quality or their complex setup and limited flexibility.[1,2]

Despite being a comparably young technique, laser processing offers specific benefits such as highly flexible, wear free cutting and so has a share in the optimization of processing costs.

Current laser processes which achieve sufficient cutting rates usually use short-pulsed or highly brilliant high-power lasers in the multi-kilowatt range. The main processing strategies used with these lasers consist of various passes of the laser beam with high speed on the identical cutting contour combined with cool down periods to avoid heat accumulation. Regardless of adapted laser machines and special processing techniques, the heat generated during the laser process can lead to heat affected zones (HAZ) adjacent to the cut face which might affect the mechanical properties and aging resistance once material specific threshold values are exceeded [3].

For an improved establishment of laser based processing within industry, not only the feed rates have to be brought to a competitive level but also material-specific temperature limits have to be met, ideally by efficient, industrially applicable and reasonably priced techniques. Threshold temperature values for machining steps are chosen rather conservatively especially in the aviation industry. In [4] it was already shown, that active cooling equipment can be a promising option to help to meet the requirements by the end users and to achieve a sufficient processing efficiency. Based on these results, the cooling set-ups will be rearranged in the present investigation to achieve better results in terms of temperatures and thermal load. The thermal evaluation will be enhanced by a second thermographic camera, monitoring the bottom surface temperatures.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

For the experiments a multidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy laminate, typically used in aviation industry, was used. The laminate consisted of 12 consolidated unidirectional (UD) prepreg layers each shifted by 45° , resulting in a total thickness of 2.2mm. The material characteristics are provided in Table 1. The specimen dimensions were kept constant at $50 \times 100 \text{mm}^2$, and a new plate was used for every new parameter or cooling arrangement to avoid influence on the heat conduction by separated fibres and removed material.

Table 1: CFRP material used for the experimental work.

Material	Fabric	Thickness (mm)	Number of layers	Fibre orientation
CF/Epoxy M21E/IMA-12K	UD prepreg	2.2	12	[0/45/90/135/0/45/135/0/135/90/45/0] _T

All investigations were conducted with a fibre-guided thin-disk high power nanosecond laser provided by TRUMPF Laser GmbH. The laser emits pulses at a wavelength of $\lambda = 1030 \text{nm}$ with a constant pulse duration of $t_p = 30 \text{ns}$. The laser can be operated at repetition rates between $f = 5 \dots 50 \text{kHz}$ but the maximum pulse energy of $E_p = 80 \text{mJ}$ and the maximum average laser power of $P_{L,avg} = 1500 \text{W}$ are available at a repetition rate of $f = 18.8 \text{kHz}$. The 2-dimensional beam movement was achieved by a galvanometer scan head (Trumpf 3D-PFO) with focussing optics. The fibre diameter of $d = 600 \mu\text{m}$, the collimating optics with a focal length $l_{f,c} = 138 \text{mm}$ and the focal length of the focussing optics of $l_f = 255 \text{mm}$ led to a focal diameter of $d_f = 1100 \mu\text{m}$. The specifications are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Laser machine and focussing optics parameter.

Parameter	Value
Maximum average laser power $P_{L,avg}$ (W)	1500
Laser wavelength λ (nm)	1030
Maximum laser pulse energy $E_{p,max}$ (mJ)	80
Laser repetition rate f (kHz)	5...50
Laser pulse duration t_p (ns)	30
Laser fibre diameter d (μm)	600
Optics focal length l_f (mm)	255
Optics Collimating focal length $l_{f,c}$ (mm)	138
Resulting focal diameter d_f (μm)	1100

In addition to the laser source and optic parts, the general setup also featured a crossjet and exhaust system used to protect the optics from process emissions and remove them respectively. In order to facilitate the four gas nozzles for cooling the top and bottom surfaces, the specimens were held in place in the assembly fixed between two pins as shown in Figure 1. The nozzle attachments in the

setup allowed a constant, pressurized air flow to be applied to both surfaces. Each pair of nozzles for the top and bottom surfaces were arranged in opposing directions. The air pressure was kept constant at $p = 5\text{bars}$. For thermal monitoring purposes, two thermographic cameras were used: one capturing the top surface, the other capturing the bottom surface synchronously. The experimental setup is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Experimental set-up.

Among different laser cutting strategies, the most common strategy to achieve a good cutting quality is multipass cutting. This strategy uses high speed scanning (v_s) and needs multiple passes on the same path, each pass only ablating a small amount of material, to cut through the material. The addition of breaks or delay times in between the (high speed) scans allows for improved heat dissipation in the material and in turn reduced thermal loads and an increase in cut quality. Based on preliminary studies, a repetition rate of $f = 18.8\text{kHz}$ was chosen for the present investigation to allow the system to operate at maximum power and pulse energy. The scanning speed was kept constant at $v_s = 1\text{m/s}$ and the delay times were varied to $t_d = [0.5 / 1 / 4]\text{s}$, representing parameter sets with high thermal load but short process times and low thermal load but long process times. For each of the delay times, there were three cooling conditions variations tested: no cooling, cooling on the top surface, and cooling on both the top and bottom surfaces. For reference purposes, a measurement without cooling was made for each delay time. The specimen dimensions were kept constant at $50 \times 100\text{mm}^2$, and a new plate was used for every new parameter or cooling arrangement to avoid influence on the heat conduction by separated fibres and removed material. The cutting contour pattern was a grid of 6 (2x3) holes with $\text{Ø}5\text{mm}$ diameter, arranged in a distance of 115mm to the next hole. The grid geometry is representative of a typical borehole pattern in the aviation industry. The pattern is shown in Figure 2. The process was stopped manually after all boreholes of the pattern were fully cut. The number of passes needed to achieve a full cut varied in a field of $n = 78 \pm 5$. The parameters and cooling set-ups used for the experiments are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Experimental parameters.

Parameter	Cooling options		
	No cooling	Top surface cooling	Top and bottom surface cooling
Laser repetition rate f (kHz)		18.8	
Scanning speed v_s (m/s)		1	
Delay time t_d (s)		0.5 / 1 / 4	
Number of passes n for a full cut (-)		78 ± 5	
Borehole diameter (mm)		5	
Borehole pattern	Grid of 2x3 holes, 115mm distance to adjacent hole		
Gas pressure p (bar)		5	

Figure 2: In-process thermographic image with bore hole pattern and measurement point used in the analysis.

The surface temperatures were detected by two synchronized TIM 640 thermographic cameras from Micro-Epsilon GmbH providing a resolution of 640x480 pixel at a 32Hz frame rate (see specifications in Table 4). The top surface camera was positioned at a distance of $s = 236\text{mm}$ and an angle of incidence of $\alpha = 26.7^\circ$ while the bottom surface camera was positioned at a distance of $s = 272\text{mm}$ and an angle of incidence of $\alpha = 22.2^\circ$. Since the top and bottom surfaces differ in surface texture as a result of the manufacturing process, the emission factors for both surfaces were calibrated by applying a special paint. The emission factor of the top surface was found to be $\epsilon_{\text{top}} = 90.5$ and the emission factor of the bottom surface was found to be $\epsilon_{\text{bot}} = 92.5$. These factors were kept constant for the duration of the experiments. For the temperature evaluation, a fixed point between the two holes in the middle section of the borehole pattern was chosen (see Figure 2). This point was observed to be in the area with the largest heat accumulation.

Table 4. Specifications of the Micro-Epsilon TIM 640 thermographic camera.

Micro-Epsilon TIM 640	
Detector type	FPA
Detector resolution (Pixel)	640x480
Spectral range (μm)	7.5...13
Measuring range ($^\circ\text{C}$)	-20...900
Thermal sensitivity, NETD (mK)	75
Measurement accuracy	$\pm 2\%$ of mean value; min. 2°C
Picture frequency at full frame (Hz)	32

The material modification generated by the thermal load is commonly referred to as the heat affected zone (HAZ) and can be visualized and evaluated by cross-section micrographs of the laser cut structures. The measurement of the HAZ is based on the procedure described in [3] or [4]. Here, the maximum visible area of the HAZ was measured by image processing and then divided by the material thickness to obtain a mean width of the HAZ. Similar to the temperature measurement point, the measurement of the HAZ was done for two holes located in the middle section of the borehole pattern (see cut A-A in Figure 2), which was observed to be the area with the largest heat accumulation. From this cross-section four HAZ values were obtained. A mean value and a standard deviation were calculated. An exemplary cross-section micrograph showing the HAZ on one cut side of a single borehole is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Cross-section micrograph of a laser drilled CFRP specimen showing the heat affected zone (HAZ).

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For the thermal load evaluation, the temperature profile of the measurement point shown in Figure 2 were filtered by their local minimum temperature after the delay time of each laser pass. This procedure will be described in the following paragraph. The temperature profile will then be compared for each configuration given in Table 3. An exemplary overall time-dependent temperature profile as recorded by the thermographic camera is shown in Figure 4. A generally upward-sloping temperature course (Figure 4, I) can be observed as long as the heat input by the laser processing exceeds the heat dissipation by free convection. Once the boreholes are partially cut or boreholes are fully cut while for others a few more repetitions are required, the amount of laser energy absorbed by the material decreases and the temperature course slopes downwards until the end of the process (Figure 4, II). While material is being removed and the laser is on, local temperature peaks (Figure 4, III) can be observed. Each local peak can be associated with a single laser pass of the 6 borehole pattern. The difference in height between the temperature peaks or local saddles points can be attributed to the cutting process emission and hot fumes blown into the point of measurement of the thermographic camera when the laser is on. The time delay that follows each laser pass is shown in Figure 4, IV in between peaks where the material is able to dissipate heat before the next pass starts. Since the height of the local peaks does not represent a reliable metric for evaluation, the evaluation of the temperature profile generated from the local minimum before the last pass (Figure 4, V) can be related to the cooling options and process parameters. For the correlation with the HAZ measurements in the last stage of this paragraph, the maximum temperature achieved within the temperature profile of local minima is taken into account (Figure 4, VI).

Figure 4: Time-dependent thermography temperature monitoring graph, details in the temperature profile and local minimum temperatures used for the final analysis.

Figure 5: Local minimum temperatures on top and bottom (back) of the CFRP specimen for a delay time of $t_d = 0.5s$ and varying cooling options.

Figure 5 shows the temperature profiles produced with a $t_d = 0.5s$ for various cooling configurations. For the trial done without any cooling, the recorded temperatures reached relatively high values of $T > 200^\circ C$, even exceeding glass transition temperature of this high performance epoxy ($T_{g,M21E} = 195^\circ C$). Furthermore, it can be seen that the temperature profiles for the top and bottom surfaces were nearly identical; the small temperature difference can be assigned to decreased heat dissipation by slightly inhibited free convection on the bottom surface. Unlike the other cooling setups, a downward temperature trend cannot be seen in the final cutting stages as is present for the configurations with cooling. When applying an air flow on the top surface only, the temperatures on the top side can be reduced to $T \sim 125^\circ C$ while the temperatures on the bottom remain on a clearly higher level around $T \sim 150^\circ C$ due to the lack of forced convection. A distinct temperature drop to $T \sim 90^\circ C$ was measured for air flow cooling on both sides of the sample. As was seen in the trial without cooling, the top and bottom surfaces also follow the same temperature trends for this trial.

When evaluating temperature profiles for the trials with $t_d = 1s$ delay times (shown in Figure 6), it can be seen that the general behavior is similar to that of Figure 5. The highest temperature level is again measured for processing without cooling ($T \sim 190^\circ C$), while the lowest temperature level is achieved when applying gas flow cooling on both material surfaces ($T \sim 70^\circ C$). For both setups the temperature courses are similar when comparing the top and bottom surface temperatures. For the trial done with only top surface cooling, the overall process temperature lies in the middle of the range between the temperature trends of the other two trials, with the exception that again a temperature difference of $T \sim 25^\circ C$ is observed between the material top and bottom surfaces. Independent of the cooling setup, the influence of an increased delay time can be seen by a $T \sim 20^\circ C$ reduction in overall process temperature, meaning a reduction of maximum 22% when comparing the values for cooling on both sides. In comparison to this, the reduction by applying gas flow cooling on both sides is more than 60%.

Figure 6: Local minimum temperatures on top and bottom (back) of the CFRP specimen for a delay time of $t_d = 1s$ and varying cooling options.

Figure 7: Local minimum temperatures on top and bottom (back) of the CFRP specimen for a delay time of $t_d = 4s$ and varying cooling options.

Figure 8: Local minimum temperatures on the top side of the CFRP specimen for top and bottom cooling for varying delay times.

If the delay time between the passes is extended to $t_p = 4s$, the temperature is again distinctly reduced (see Figure 7). With the additional delay time, it can be seen that without cooling, the maximum process temperature decreases to $T \sim 110C^\circ$. Similarly, with the addition of top and bottom surface cooling, the maximum process temperature further decreases to $T = 43.3C^\circ$ with $t_d = 4s$.

Although increasing the delay time positively influences the process temperatures and would seem

to be a good parameter to adjust heat dissipation and the resultant thermal load, as can be seen in Figure 8, the delay time also has a significant influence on process duration. Since the amount of time the laser is on is comparably short due to the fast scanning speeds used for multipass cutting, it can be seen that process time is greatly sensitive to changes in delay time.

In a last step, the achievable cutting quality in terms of the HAZ is related to the temperatures, parameter settings and cooling options. In Figure 9 the mean width of the HAZ and corresponding maximum temperatures on both the top and bottom surfaces, for the different delay times and cooling options is shown. Overall, it can be seen that there is a strong correlation between surface temperature and HAZ. As such, the largest HAZ values obtained correspond to the trials with the highest maximum surface temperatures. These are generally represented by the trials without cooling, or the setups with only top cooling and short delay times ($t_p = 0.5s$). Conversely, the smallest recorded HAZ values are found where the trials involved cooling on both top and bottom surfaces, over the range of tested delay times, all of which showed the lowest temperature values. For constant delay times a HAZ reduction is achieved by applying cooling on both material surfaces. This method is revealed to be even more effective than the extension of the delay times from $t_p = 0.5s$ to $t_p = 4s$, while at the same time not influencing the process efficiency. This leads to the conclusion that the use of this cooling method should be preferred to the extension of delay times.

Figure 9: Mean width of the HAZ and corresponding maximum temperatures on the material top and bottom surface for different delay times and cooling options.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, investigations were carried out on the impact of cost-effective and easy-to-apply cooling options on the thermal load during laser processing of CFRP. The experimental setup featured a varied forced convection air cooled set up, where trials with cooling were carried out with either air flow over the top surface or both the top and bottom surfaces. As a reference point, the trials were compared with those done in absence of any forced convection cooling. The three cooling variations were carried out using a range of delay times implemented between each pass in the multipass cutting strategy. The effectiveness was evaluated by recording the temperatures on the material top and bottom surfaces synchronously and by a heat affected zone (HAZ) measurement on cross-section micrographs. A material and borehole pattern geometry commonly used in the aviation industry was chosen for the experiments.

Based on the results, it can be clearly stated that both the cooling method and the delay time settings have a strong influence on material temperature level and resulting HAZ. During processing both methods are able to bring down the temperatures to a level far below the glass transition temperature of the M21E epoxy and to distinctly reduce the width of the heat affected zone. The

lowest values were obtained for cooling on both material surfaces throughout all delay time settings, while the highest reduction was achieved by cooling on both surfaces and extended delay times. However, it was pointed out that the extension of the delay times does have a strong influence on the process duration. Thus, the thermal load reduction by simple, cost-effective and easy-to-integrate cooling options should be preferred to the extension of delay times. It was shown that enhanced cooling is not only necessary for meeting temperature threshold values but it is highly recommended to achieve sufficient process durations.

Real parts might have not only one pattern of boreholes but various patterns distributed over a larger CFRP structure. Future investigations should include the aspect of a working field enlargement by stage systems and the effect on efficient processing strategies.

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